

Mining Correlated Biclusters from Web Usage Data using Discrete Firefly Algorithm based Biclustering Approach

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Abstract : For the past one decade, biclustering has become a popular data mining technique not only in the field of biological data analysis but also in other applications like text mining, market data analysis etc., with high-dimensional two-way datasets. Biclustering clusters both rows and columns of a dataset simultaneously, as opposed to traditional clustering which clusters either rows or columns of a dataset. It retrieves subgroups of objects that are similar in one subgroup of variables and different in the remaining variables. Firefly Algorithm (FA) is a recently-proposed metaheuristic inspired by the collective behavior of fireflies. This paper provides a preliminary assessment of the discrete version of FA (DFA) while coping with the task of mining coherent and large volume biclusters from a web usage dataset. For this purpose, experiments were conducted on two web usage datasets from a public dataset repository whereby the performance of FA was compared with that exhibited by other population-based metaheuristics called binary Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO). The results achieved demonstrate the usefulness of DFA while tackling the biclustering problem.

Keywords : Biclustering, Firefly Algorithm, Discrete Firefly Algorithm, Binary Particle Swarm Optimization, Web usage mining, Usage profile

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